

Determinants of Adoption of Technology-based Payment Systems among University Students

Faiz Amrullah Ibnu Purwanto

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0656-9817>

Budi Rustandi Kartawinata

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4670-1019>

***Mahir Pradana**

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4761-2891>

**Department of Business Administration, School of Economics and Business,
Telkom University, Bandung 40257, Indonesia**

*Corresponding Author Email: mahirpradana@telkomuniversity.ac.id

Abstract

Background: The rapid development of digital payment systems in Indonesia has transformed the way transactions are conducted, with Quick Response (QR) payment emerging as a popular method. QR payment systems leverage the convenience of smartphones to enable cashless transactions, allowing users to make payments by scanning QR codes through mobile applications. This technology aligns with Indonesia's push toward becoming a cashless society, driven by the increasing penetration of smartphones, the proliferation of fintech solutions, and the government's commitment to advancing financial inclusion.

Objective: This study aimed to explore consumer behaviour in digital transformation and financial inclusion among university students.

Methodology: The study made use of a descriptive survey research design to achieve its aim. A structured questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. The sample consisted of 100 university students. The data for the study were analysed quantitatively, and the results were presented in tables and figures for visual illustration.

Results: The study's results show that facilitating conditions, ease of use, and risk perception have a significant effect on the behavioural intention to use QR in payments. Not all respondents have

the same conditions when making payments through technology-based systems, which also affects their behavioural intention to continue using cashless payments, influenced by the circumstances and conditions under which they make payments.

Conclusion: We conclude that facilitating conditions, ease of use, and risk perception are influential factors in determining behavioural intention towards payments through QR systems.

Unique Contribution: This research contributes to the understanding of the factors such as perceived ease of use, facilitating conditions, and risk perception on university students' behavioural intention to use QR payment systems, while also highlighting the challenges faced in adopting this technology in Indonesia.

Key Recommendation: To enhance QR payment adoption among university students in Indonesia, it is recommended that digital literacy be improved through targeted education, user interfaces be streamlined for a better experience, security features be strengthened to alleviate risk perceptions, accessibility be ensured for all students, and collaborations be fostered with fintech companies for tailored solutions.

Keywords: Finance, digital payment, Indonesia, behavioural intention

Introduction

The Bank of Indonesia Regulation (PBI No. 11/12/PBI/2009) catalyst behind the shift from cash payments to non-cash or cashless transactions in 2009. When the Bank of Indonesia launched the National Non-Cash Movement (GNNT) in 2014, the concept of non-cash transactions was then reinforced once more (Sofwatunnisa et al., 2023). At that point, as cashless payment systems were perceived as more practical, Indonesians gradually began to replace cash with them. Previously, people carried wallets full of cash with them at all times, but nowadays, they carry bank cards, debit, or credit-only (Purwanto et al., 2024).

Quick Response (QR) applications have been around for a while; typically, QR takes two dimensions. Japan's Denso-Wave company was the first to develop the 2D barcode system. They track the auto parts made during vehicle production using QR codes (Harva, 2024). The development of smartphones has come a long way in the last few years. Twenty-one years have passed since mobile phones and the internet paired in 2001, which is sufficient to transform the world into a new way of life and put the entire world at our fingertips (Yunani et al., 2024). Right now, in order to use a QR code, you have to scan it using a camera, like the one on a smartphone. Occasionally, in order to read the QR code, you still need to download a third-party app. Typically, a QR code is used to store a link that is subsequently sent to a browser. Still, advances in QR technology allow for the storage of text, images, and even apps. When the camera decodes the code and the information inside the QR appears, the QR code process works. After that, a few steps are needed to generate the desired QR code (Wardhana et al., 2022).

The cashless payment system was created by utilising technology to make payments and, of course, save money over the cash version. In addition to using a debit or credit card, QR codes have now been used in cashless payments and have become widely accepted in the business sector (Baier-Fuentes, et al., 2019). In order to make payments simpler and more useful for business owners, new payment methods have also been created using QR codes. Typically, a bank account

and an e-wallet are connected to the QR code. The buyer pays directly to the merchant through the merchant's account. GPN is in charge of QR payment usage in Indonesia (Wardhana, et al., 2021). A national integration of different payment instruments and channels is the goal of the GPN, a system of standards, switching, and services built with a set of mechanisms and regulations. In order to create an interbank network that is integrated and interconnected, Bank Indonesia launched the GPN. This network consists of a combination of payment systems and banking transaction channels. On December 4, 2017, in Jakarta, the National Payment Gateway was approved and opened under Bank Indonesia Regulation No. 19/8/PBI/2017 and Members of the Board of Governors Regulation No. 19/10/PADG/2017 (Auer et al., 2020).

Since humans first began trading in antiquity, cash payments have been made. Originally, exchange-valued goods like grain, gold, or silver were used to make cash payments. However, as time went on, coins and banknotes were also utilised as forms of payment with cash (Sofwatunnisa et al., 2024). In the past, cash payments were frequently made in person, with the buyer giving the seller cash in exchange for the goods or services rendered. With technological advancements, cash payments can now also be made online with credit cards or bank transfers, for example (Purwanto et al., 2024).

Money has evolved and is still seen as a practical means of making small-value payments. Large sums of cash can be challenging to carry around when making big purchases. Because of the frequent robberies, thefts, and counterfeiting, carrying large sums of cash is also regarded as risky (Chatterjee, 2018). As a result, people are reluctant to keep or carry large amounts of cash. However, many people still prefer to make cash payments, particularly in developing nations with an underdeveloped financial infrastructure. Additionally, some people think that paying with cash is safer and simpler. Globally, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a terrible effect on nearly every aspect of life. One of the effects of COVID-19's existence is the economic one. Make it mandatory for everyone in business to modify their business governance. However, businesspeople were able to find ways to adjust to the current circumstances once things began to improve, or you could say that they were entering the post-pandemic period. starting with the payment system and moving on to the business platform. Due to its practicality and ease of use, non-cash payment systems are preferred by business people (Davis, 1989).

To avoid physical contact during the pandemic, people gradually started to use cashless payments. Research from the Bank for International Settlements (BIS Bulletins) indicates that compared to frequently touched objects, there is very little chance of the virus spreading through cash (Featherman & Pavlou, 2003). Despite the extremely low likelihood of transmission, there is no harm in protecting yourself by taking preventive measures. One way to decrease this contact is to modify the payment method from a cash-based to a non-cash one, such as using QR payments. Why not use a credit or debit card instead? When making payments with a card, there is still physical contact. However, using QR codes is different; instead of using an e-wallet to make payments, we need to scan the code.

In the context of the rapid growth of the digital sector and the need for MSMEs to adapt post-COVID-19, it is crucial to understand how technologies like Quick Response Codes (QRIS) can contribute to their business sustainability. QRIS not only offers efficient payment solutions but

also has the potential to enhance consumer trust and loyalty. Previous research has highlighted the increasing adoption of QRIS across various industries and its positive effects on payment processing and customer engagement. To this end, we conduct a pilot study aimed at providing in-depth insights into the influence of QRIS among the Telkom University student, laying the groundwork for further analysis. The following is data obtained from Google Scholar with the top 5 citations and top 5 authors in the context of QRIS usage.

Table 1: Top Cited Previous Research

Citations	First Authors	Titles	Year	Journal
102	A. Kadim	Financial Management System (QRIS) based on UTAUT Model Approach in Jabodetabek	2022	International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research
93	Fulshah Chohan	Building Customer Loyalty In Digital Transaction Using QR Code: Quick Response Code Indonesian Standard (QRIS)	2022	Journal of Distribution Science
59	Ni Putu Ani Karniawati	Community perception of using qr code payment in era new normal	2021	PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology

Table 2 Top 5 Authors

Numbers of Paper	Authors	Titles	Year	Publications
3	Edi Wijayanto	Application of the TAM Model and Financial Literacy on Interest in QRIS Digital Payments (Study on Semarang State Polytechnic Students)	2024	Formosa Journal of Science and Technology
2	Adisthy Shabrina Nurqamarani	Revolutionizing Payment Systems: The Integration of TRAM and Trust in QRIS Adoption for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia.	2024	Journal of Information Systems Engineering & Business Intelligence
		Adoption of QRIS as a Digital Payment Mode in the Culinary Subsector: A Conceptual Framework Study	2023	Proceedings of the 5th Open Society Conference
2	Drajad Wiryawan	Analysis of Factors Influencing the Use of QRIS on Museum Visitors with the Extended TAM Model	2023	11th International Conference on Cyber and IT Service

		Management (CITSM)
Factors influencing e-wallet users' perception on payment transaction security: Evaluation on quick response Indonesia standard	2021	Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Technology and Digital Applications (ICITDA 2021)

Literature Review

Perceived Ease of Use

"The degree to which a person believes that using technology will be free from effort" is the definition of PEOU (Davis, 1989). The degree to which a person feels that a specific technology or system is simple to use is known as perceived ease of use. People's subjective evaluations, which are influenced by their personal experiences and expectations, can greatly influence how they feel about and use a technology (Iriani & Andjarwati, 2020).

PEOU is defined more precisely as the degree of ease and confidence users experience while learning about and utilizing FinTech services. (Zhongqing Hu, 2019). Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant impact on behavioural intention to use technology (Davis, 1989). Users are frequently asked to rate how easy they think a system or piece of technology is to use in surveys or questionnaires in order to gauge perceived ease of use. The system's user interface, the simplicity and clarity of its instructions, and the user's previous experience and familiarity with similar systems are some of the factors that can affect how easy a system is perceived to be to use.

Additionally, there is a strong correlation between PEOU and the desire to use technology services, such as FinTech mobile payment services. (Ahmad Daragmeh, 2021). Low perceived ease of use can cause frustration and technology abandonment, whereas high perceived ease of use can boost user satisfaction and adoption. In order to improve the perceived ease of use for users, designers and developers of technology systems work hard to provide interfaces and interactions that are clear, uncomplicated, and intuitive.

In Indonesia, the development of new products and services must take user-friendliness into consideration. In order to enhance user experience and facilitate accessibility, it is imperative, for instance, in online banking services. The development of mobile banking applications by numerous Indonesian banks has facilitated online bill payment, transfer, and balance check functions for clients. Ease of use is a factor that developers in Indonesia must consider when creating new products or services. The public can obtain and use goods and services more readily if ease of use is given consideration.

H1: Perceived Ease of Use has a positive relationship with behavioural intention to use cashless payment systems among university students.

Facilitating condition

The belief that customers have in the tools and assistance at their disposal to carry out an action is referred to as a "facilitating condition" (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Some studies found that (Morosan & Defranco, 2016) on the use of mobile payments have confirmed the importance of enabling conditions on behavioural intention, whereas some others (Oliveira et al., 2016) discovered that the influence of the enabling conditions on the behavioural intention was not significant. The term "facilitating condition" in the context of payments refers to elements or circumstances that facilitate the completion of a payment transaction by people or companies. These conditions can be both internal and external to the payment process and may include:

- **User-friendly payment interfaces:** Customers are more likely to complete transactions on payment platforms that are simple to use and navigate.
- **Convenience:** Transactions can be facilitated by payment methods that are easy to use and easily accessible. For instance, carrying cash or writing a check are frequently viewed as less convenient than making mobile payments with a smartphone.
- **Security:** Strong security features, like fraud detection and encryption, provided by payment processors can foster customer trust and speed up transactions.
- **Usability:** Payment systems that are simple to operate and navigate can save time and effort and raise the possibility that a transaction will be completed successfully. **Integration:** Payment systems that are integrated with other systems, such as online stores, can facilitate transactions by reducing the amount of manual data entry required and making the payment process more streamlined.
- **International Capabilities:** Payment systems that support several currencies and languages can make it easier for companies to transact with clients in various geographical areas.

Businesses can lower transaction costs and errors, boost customer satisfaction, and increase the likelihood of successful transactions by identifying and addressing facilitating conditions in the payment process.

H2 Facilitating conditions have a positive relationship with behavioural intention to use cashless payment systems among university students.

Risk Perception

According to (Featherman & Pavlou, 2003); Financial risk is the potential for monetary loss from initial product purchases and continuing staff maintenance. The total amount of money lost when purchasing goods or services, as well as the portion of that loss that is sustained throughout the use of those goods or services. Furthermore, according to Suryani and Aminah (2023), financial risks result in losses from financial transactions that customers undertake. In situations where there is a substantial financial risk, online transactions are discouraged. Customers are satisfied when they anticipate, and some of their concerns don't materialise, which indicates that financial risk has a major influence on customer satisfaction. This is how the relationship between financial risk and customer satisfaction can be explained.

H3: Risk Perception has a positive relationship with behavioural intention to use cashless payment systems among university students.

Behavioural Intention

In order to understand and forecast the relationship between attitude and behaviour, the theory of reasoned action (Wardhana et al., 2021) is put forth. This theory holds that behavioural intentions

govern an individual's behaviour. Greater behavioural intentions indicate a higher likelihood of individual behaviour, so behavioural intentions can be thought of as a person's potential behavioural tendencies. When a consumer intends to buy a product or service, they mean that they intend to finish the payment process and make the purchase. This is known as behavioural intention. It expresses the person's desire to pay for the goods, their opinion of how simple it is to complete the payment process, and their sense of control over it.

An individual's behavioural intention to pay for a product can be influenced by a number of factors, such as their level of trust in the payment system, how simple and convenient they think the payment process is, and how secure and private they believe their payment information is.

The term "consumer behavioural intention" describes a person's inclination or willingness to act in the near future to use or buy a good or service. Consumer behaviour intention is a reflection of an individual's cognitive and affective assessment of a good or service, as well as their personal beliefs about their capacity to purchase or utilise it.

For instance, a customer's behavioural intention to finish the payment process is likely to be high if they feel secure and confident that their payment information is protected, trust the payment system, and find the payment process to be simple and convenient. However, a customer's behavioural intention to finish the payment process is likely to be low if they don't trust the payment system, think it's a difficult or inconvenient process, or think their payment information isn't secure.

Methodology

Research Design

This research employs a quantitative methodology. When something is described as quantitative, it emphasises objective measurements and statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data gathered through surveys, polls, and other methods of data collection, as well as the use of computational techniques to manipulate statistical data that has already been collected. The goal of quantitative research is to collect numerical data, generalise it to other populations, or provide an explanation for a specific phenomenon. Since Google Forms was used to collect the data, it is included in the online distribution. Scale is being used in the quantitative analysis of this study. Respondents will find it easier to choose an answer when there are five options available to them for the question that relates to their particular life experience. The scale, which ranges from scale 1 (strongly disagree) to scale 5 (strongly agree), depends on the respondent's response.

Sample and Data Collection

The respondent's eligibility to complete the Google form's questionnaire is limited to students enrolled at Telkom University in Bandung, West Java. The Telkom University students were selected as respondents because the purpose of this study is to find out how frequently students use QR payments once the pandemic situation has passed. Due to the fact that during previous pandemics, people tended to use QR codes instead of physical cash transactions to reduce physical contact during payment. These respondents have agreed to participate in the questionnaire voluntarily and without coercion. The confidentiality of the information they submit is assured. The distribution of this survey took place from July through October of 2023.

Data Analysis

PLS (Partial Least Square) was used in this study's data analysis, and the Smart PLS 3.0 program was used to process the data. A measurement model (outer model), a structural model (inner model), and the Goodness of Fit (GoF) criteria make up the PLS measurement model. PLS looks for influence or a relationship between these constructs in order to test predictive relationships between them.

Figure 1 (Research Model)

Results

Validity tests are a procedure for determining the degree to which a tool can measure what it is intended to measure (Hair et al., 2016). In other words, a validity test evaluates how well a tool can provide precise and pertinent data pertaining to the concept or variable it intends to measure. In order to analyse PLS, two sub-models are applied, namely the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model). The measurement model is used to assess the validity and reliability of the model, while the structural model is used to test causality or to test the model's predictions (Harva et al., 2024).

Outer Model

Convergent validity testing in partial structural analysis (PLS-SEM) or other statistical approaches is one component of concept validity testing. This is a reference to the degree to which the indicators used to assess a specific construct should be interrelated and assess the same item or at least closely related things (Hair et al., 2016). Discriminant validity takes place when two distinct instruments that assess two constructs that are supposed to be uncorrelated result in uncorrelated results. A loading factor value greater than 0.7 is the optimal value, indicating that the indication is reliable for gauging the constructed object. Loading factor values greater than 0.5 are still recognised in empirical research. AVE assesses how effectively the indicators used to measure the latent variable describe the concept. Indicators that accurately describe the construct being measured have an AVE value less than 0.5. There are two techniques to assess a construct's reliability using reflecting indicators: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, often known as Dillon-Goldstein's (Imam Ghozali, 2015). The Composite reliability value, or alpha, must

generally be more than 0.7, if a value of 0.6 is acceptable. The outcomes of the validity and reliability test conducted with the SmartPLS software are as follows.

Table 3: Evaluation of measurement model

Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Facilitating Condition	0.817	0.733
Risk Perception	0.778	0.691
Perceived Ease of Use	0.812	0.724
Behavioral Intention	0.742	0.660

Strong reliability is defined as each Cronbach's Alpha or Composite Reliability output value being greater than 0.7. The four latent variables (Facilitating Condition, Risk Perception, Perceived Ease of Use, and Behavioural Intention) have CA and CR values of more than 0.7, indicating that the data is dependable and all variables have a high degree of reliability. Additionally, Table 1 demonstrates that all four variables—Risk Perception, Perceived Ease of Use, Behavioural Intention, and Facilitating Condition—have AVE values higher than the required minimum of 0.5, indicating that they satisfy the validity requirements.

If the outer loading indicator is greater than 0.7, then convergent validity is deemed to be good. However, if the outer loading value is found to fall between 0.5 and 0.6, it is deemed adequate to meet the convergent validity requirement. If certain indicators are found to be non-significant at the time of the validity test, such as having an outer loading value less than 0.5, they must be removed (Wardhana et al., 2021). Table 2 shows that there are no outer loading indicators with a value less than 0.5. This means that further analysis can be conducted using the indicators now that their use for research has been authorised. The measurement of discriminant validity is done by cross-loading with the construct. An indicator is considered to have discriminant validity if its value on one variable is higher than its value on other variables. This is the case with the cross-loading indicator. The outcomes of factor cross-loading with SmartPLS software are as follows.

Table 4 Discriminant Validity

Indicator	Behavioral Intention	Facilitating Condition	Perceived Ease of Use	Risk of Perception
BI1	0.825	0.413	0.538	0.497
BI2	0.785	0.409	0.521	0.496
BI3	0.827	0.505	0.512	0.472
FC1	0.387	0.826	0.412	0.272
FC2	0.514	0.931	0.484	0.467
FC3	0.483	0.806	0.339	0.509

PEoU1	0.631	0.329	0.866	0.369
PEoU2	0.557	0.527	0.883	0.483
PEoU3	0.425	0.382	0.801	0.360
RP1	0.433	0.458	0.241	0.779
RP2	0.601	0.418	0.563	0.893
RP3	0.440	0.374	0.327	0.818
Source: Author’s Result (2024)				

Table 2 demonstrates that it satisfies the cross-loading requirements, with each variable having the highest cross-loading value among the variables it produces. Therefore, it is possible to draw the conclusion that this study has good discriminant validity in the indicators that are used.

Inner Model

Evaluation Structure Model

The inner model is a structural model that predicts cause-and-effect relationships between variables, often known as latent variables or components that are not immediately measurable. The structural model (inner model) describes the causal link between latent variables, which was created using the theory's fundamental principles. The structural model (inner model) is tested using SMART PLS's Bootstrapping procedure. One of the tests for structural models used in this work was R Square on endogenous components (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The R Square value represents the coefficient of determination for the endogenous construct. In accordance with (Hair et al., 2016), the R-squared values are 0.67 (strong), 0.33 (moderate), and 0.1. The R-squared results are shown in the following table.

Table 5 R-Square

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
BI	0.554	0.540
Source: Author’s Result (2024)		

Table 3 indicates that the behavioural intention R-squared value is 0.554. This demonstrates that the Behavioural Intention variable influences 0.554, with external factors influencing the remaining 0.446. Consequently, only 55.4% of behavioural intention could be explained by the variables employed in this study; other factors could explain the remaining 44.6%. By examining the probability value, hypotheses are tested. With an alpha of 5%, the p-value for probability values is 0.05. If the p-value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted; if it is greater than 0.05, the hypothesis is rejected (Hair et al., 2016). The path coefficient table in the SmartPLS outputs contains SmartPLS outputs. In structural model testing, the applicability of predictive models can be assessed using t-statistical values between independent and dependent variables.

Table 6: Hypothesis Test

Variable	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Facilitating Condition -> Behavioral Intention	0.196	1.826	0.068
Perceived Ease of Use -> Behavioral Intention	0.402	4.099	0.000
Risk Perception -> Behavioral Intention	0.313	3.493	0.000

Figure 2 (Output Bootstrapping)

The following are the outcomes of testing each hypothesis, as indicated by the above table:

Facilitating Condition on Behavioural Intentions

The path coefficient value is positive 0.196, indicating a positive influence on behavioural intention, according to the path coefficient table. The effect is not significant, as evidenced by the t-statistic of 1.826, which is less than 1.96, and the p-value of 0.068, which is greater than 0.05. This indicates that the facilitating condition will be rejected since it does not match the requirements and does not significantly affect behavioural intention. This is in line with research conducted by Le (2022) on Vietnamese society, which suggests that Facilitating Conditions do not have a significant effect on behavioural intention. Nonetheless, this outcome does not inherently imply that the Facilitating Condition lacks significance. If mobile QR payment offers more resources and supportive services than other forms of payment, consumers may be more inclined to use it. Simply put, Facilitating Conditions, which include security, Internet access, and knowledge, are regarded as the facilities that are available for all mobile services and online payments.

The implications of these findings are multifaceted. First, businesses and developers of mobile payment solutions should recognise that simply having facilitating conditions in place is not enough to guarantee increased behavioural intention. While these conditions are essential, they

must be coupled with effective communication strategies that highlight the advantages and ease of using such systems. For example, providing clear instructions, robust customer support, and demonstrating the security features of mobile QR payments can enhance consumer confidence. In addition, future research could explore the nuanced relationship between facilitating conditions and behavioural intention in different contexts or demographic groups. Understanding how specific facilitating conditions interact with other variables could lead to more tailored strategies that encourage the adoption and usage of mobile payment solutions.

Perceived Ease of use on Behavioral Intention

The path coefficient value of 0.402, as indicated in the path coefficients table, demonstrates a positive effect on behavioural intention. This suggests that as the perceived ease of use increases, individuals' intentions to engage in certain behaviours also rise. The accompanying p-value of 0.000 is significantly lower than the conventional threshold of 0.05, providing strong evidence against the null hypothesis. Additionally, the t-statistic of 4.099 exceeds the critical value of 1.96, further confirming the statistical significance of this relationship. The results demonstrate that perceived ease of use positively and significantly influences behavioural intention. This is consistent with prior research, including that of Kongarchapatara & Rodjanatara (2018), which also demonstrated that perceived ease of use favourably affects behavioural intention in diverse circumstances. The reliability of these findings highlights the significance of perceived ease of use in influencing user behaviour, especially regarding the adoption of new technologies.

The implications of these findings are substantial for businesses and policymakers. By recognising that perceived ease of use directly affects behavioural intention, organisations can focus on enhancing user experiences and simplifying processes to encourage adoption. For instance, in the context of digital payment systems like QRIS, ensuring that the technology is user-friendly and accessible can significantly boost users' willingness to engage with the system. Furthermore, these results highlight the need for targeted educational initiatives that inform potential users about the benefits and ease of utilizing such technologies. By fostering a better understanding of how simple and intuitive these systems can be, stakeholders can enhance user confidence and encourage broader participation.

Risk Perception on Behavioural Intention

The analysis revealed a path coefficient value of 0.313, indicating a positive effect of perceived risk on behavioural intention, supported by a p-value of 0.000 and a t-statistic of 3.493, both indicating a significant impact. Consequently, it is acknowledged that perceived risk influences behavioural intention. However, contrary to this finding, Panupong and Rawin (2021) showed that there is no causal relationship between perceived risk and intention to use or continue using QR code payments. Although the sub-constructs of perceived risk, including financial, performance, time, psychological, and privacy risks, were acknowledged, the results showed that perceived risk was not significantly correlated with behavioural intention toward QR code payments. This alignment highlights an important insight that perceived risk is acknowledged as an influential factor in determining behavioural intention, while perceived risk is acknowledged as an influential factor in determining behavioural intention. Previous research has shown that it may not have a meaningful impact on actual use or continued engagement with QR code payment systems. Thus, this study adds to the growing body of evidence suggesting that, despite perceived risk, users may

still choose to adopt and utilise QR code payments, reflecting a shift in consumer behaviour that warrants further exploration.

The findings of this study have several important implications for stakeholders involved in the promotion and implementation of QR code payment systems. First, the positive and significant impact of perceived risk on behavioural intention suggests that while users are aware of the risks associated with digital payments, these concerns do not necessarily hinder their willingness to adopt the technology. This suggests consumers are becoming more familiar and comfortable with QR code payments, which businesses can capitalize on. To capitalise on this trend, organisations should prioritise user education and awareness campaigns that emphasise the security and benefits of QR code payments. By addressing the different dimensions of perceived risk such as financial, performance, psychological, and privacy risks businesses can help alleviate consumer concerns and increase trust in digital payment solutions. Transparent communication about the security measures in place, such as encryption and fraud protection, can further reassure users and encourage adoption.

Conclusion

Based on the research findings, we can conclude that Perceived Ease of Use has a positive and significant effect on Behavioural Intention towards the QR Code Payment System. This highlights the importance of easy-to-use features in driving adoption. In addition, Perceived Risk also positively influences Behavioural Intention, indicating that users acknowledge potential risks, such as fraud, but still choose to use QRIS due to its convenience. In contrast, although Facilitating Conditions have a positive effect, they do not significantly influence Behavioural Intention. This suggests that while enabling measures, such as access to technology and security, are considered important, they are not the primary drivers of adoption.

The study also revealed that most respondents had prior experience with QRIS, indicating that usage has become a habit for many. This habitual use reinforces the idea that once users become accustomed to a payment method, they are likely to continue using it, even when faced with perceived risks. The development of this habit suggests a positive feedback loop as more people adopt QRIS and share their experiences, which can increase trust and further adoption among potential users. In summary, although Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Risk significantly influence Behavioural Intention towards QRIS, the role of Facilitating Conditions is less prominent. These findings emphasise the importance of improving user experience through ease of use while addressing user concerns about safety and security. In addition, cultivating an environment that encourages regular use through positive experiences can further strengthen QRIS as a preferred payment method. Future efforts should focus on educating users about security measures and improving the overall infrastructure to build trust and encourage wider adoption of the QR code payment system.

Reference

- Auer, R., Cornelli, G., & Frost, J. (2020). Covid-19, cash, and the future of payments. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(10), 1–9.
- Baier-Fuentes, H., Merigó, J. M., Amorós, J. E., & Gaviria-Marín, M. (2019). International entrepreneurship: a bibliometric overview. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 15(6), 385-429. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-017-0487-y>
- Chatterjee, S. &. (2018). Space effective and encrypted QR code with sender authorized security levels. *2018 IEEE 8th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)*, 439-443.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly*, 3(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>.
- Featherman, M., & Pavlou, P. (2003). Predicting e-services adoption: A perceived risk facets perspective. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 59(4), 451-474. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1071-5819\(03\)00111-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1071-5819(03)00111-3).
- Hair, J., F., J., Sarstedt, M., Matthews, L. M., & Ringle, C. M. (2016). Identifying and treating unobserved heterogeneity with FIMIX-PLS: Part I Method. *European Business Review*, 28 (1), 63-76. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-09-2015-0094>
- Harva, Z. B., Pradana, M., Yunani, A., Tikupadang, W., & Kurnianingrum, D. (2024). Green purchase behavior: a preliminary study. In *International Conference on Medical Imaging, Electronic Imaging, Information Technologies, and Sensors (MIEITS 2024)*, 13188, 322-327. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3030878>.
- Iriani, S. S., & Andjarwati, A. L. (2020). Analysis of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and perceived risk toward online shopping in the era of Covid-19 pandemic. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(12)313-320.
- Kongarchapatara, B., & Rodjanatara, C. (2018). Factors affecting adoption versus behavioral intention to use QR code payment application. In *2018 International Conference on E-Commerce, e-Administration, e-Society, e-Education, and e-Technology*, Osaka, Japan. <https://www.cm.mahidol.ac.th/research/index.php/publications>.
- Le, X. C. (2022). The diffusion of mobile QR-code payment: an empirical evaluation for a pandemic. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 14(4) 617-636. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJBA-07-2021-0329>
- Morosan, C., & Defranco, A. L. (2016). It's about time: Revisiting UTAUT2 to examine consumers' intentions to use NFC mobile payments in hotels. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 53, 17-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2015.11.003>
- Oliveira, T., Thomas, M., Baptista, G., & Campos, F. (2016). Mobile payment: Understanding the determinants of customer adoption and intention to recommend the technology. *Computers in human behavior*, 61, 404-414.
- Purwanto, F. A. I., Kartawinata, B. R., Pradana, M., & Akbar, A. (2024). Quick response codes' benefits for MSMEs: a visualised bibliometric approach. *WSEAS Transactions on Computer Research*, 12, 93-98. [10.37394/232018.2024.12.8](https://doi.org/10.37394/232018.2024.12.8).

- Sofwatunnisa, A. A., Kartawinata, B. R., & Pradana, M. (2024). QR-code payment analysis: evidence from QRIS users in Indonesia. *In 2024 IEEE 22nd Student Conference on Research and Development (SCORED)* (pp. 712-715). 10.1109/SCORED64708.2024.10872728
- Sofwatunnisa, A. A., Kartawinata, B. R., Akbar, A., Pradana, M., Putra, A., & Hidayat, A. M. (2023). Quick response code as a game-changer of Indonesian digital transactions. *WSEAS Transactions on Computer Research*, *11*, 479-485. <https://doi.org/10.37394/232018.2023.11.43>.
- Suebtimrat, P., & Vonguai, R. (2021). An investigation of behavioral intention towards QR code payment in Bangkok, Thailand. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, *8*(1), 939-950. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no1.939>
- Suryani, A. P., & Aminah, W. (2023). Operating cash flow on financial distress (study on companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (Idx) for the period of 2018-2021 in the transportation and logistics sector of service companies. *Journal of Humanities and Social Studies*, *7*(3), 755-761.
- Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y., & Xu, X. (2012). Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *MIS Quarterly*, *36*(1), 157-178. 10.2307/41410412
- Wardhana, A., Kartawinata, B. R., Akbar, A., & Muslimin, I. (2021). The effect of the use of influencer on the purchase decision of MSME culinary products in indonesia (study on snack product "Kripik Belings" on Instagram). *Proceedings of the International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, (pp. 190-198). <https://doi.org/10.46254/AP01.20210098>
- Wardhana, A., Pradana, M., Kartawinata, B. R., Mas-Machuca, M., Pratomo, T. P., & Mihardjo, L. W. W. (2022). A Twitter social media analytics approach on Indonesian digital wallet service. *In 2022 International Conference Advancement in Data Science, E-learning and Information Systems (ICADEIS)*, pp. 01-05. 10.1109/ICADEIS56544.2022.10037442
- Yunani, A., Astuti, Y., Tantra, T., Nurhazizah, E., Pradana, M., Saputri, M. E., & Ahmad, M. (2024). Systematic literature review on tourism village in Indonesia. *WSEAS Transactions on Systems*, (28) 60-65. 10.37394/23202.2024.23.6.
- Zhongqing Hu, S. D. (2019). Adoption intention of fintech services for bank users: an empirical examination with an extended technology acceptance model. *Symmetry* *11*(3), 340. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym11030340>.